

Triphenylmethane Dyes derived from Quinoline, Tetrahydroquinoline, Diphenylamine and Carbazole.

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Although the condensation of various aldehydes with aromatic amines has been previously investigated, that with quinoline appears to have been very little studied. Therefore it seemed to be of interest to undertake the investigation of the reaction between quinoline and various aldehydes with a view to make a comparative study of the products derived from it and those from tetrahydroquinoline, diphenylamine and carbazole.

It is now found that two molecules of quinoline condense with one molecule of an aromatic aldehyde in the presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid on the water-bath to produce a leuco-base (I) analogous in constitution to the leuco-base of malachite green, the carbinol compound (II) being obtained by oxidation with lead peroxide, thus:

The condensation with β -resoroyl aldehyde takes place most readily (yield, 70 per cent.). In these condensations the linking with the aldehydic carbon atom takes place in position 6, since when this position is occupied, as in 6-nitroquinoline, the reaction does not take place. It seems that an acidic group in the *meta*-position in the aldehyde molecule retards the reaction to a great extent: *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde reacts with extreme difficulty while *m*-hydroxy-

benzaldehyde does not react at all. Aliphatic aldehydes, like formaldehyde and cinnamic aldehyde, could not be condensed with quinoline.

Tetrahydroquinoline, which had been previously condensed with benzaldehyde and formaldehyde (Einhorn, *Ber.*, 19, 1243, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1906, 25, 261), and *N*-methyltetrahydroquinoline have also now been condensed with various aldehydes with a view to compare their reactivities as well as the derived dyes with quinoline. It appears that the greater activity of tetrahydroquinoline and the stronger basic character of the compounds derived from it as compared with those of quinoline are due to the difference in configuration of the nitrogen atom in the two compounds, which forming part of a ring, is doubly linked in quinoline but singly linked in tetrahydroquinoline.

It is known that the reactivity of the hydrogen atom in the *para*-position to the amino-group is markedly increased if the latter is alkylated but is appreciably diminished when it is converted into -N:N- (as in azobenzene) or into -N:CH- group (as in benzylidene-aniline). Tetrahydroquinoline may be compared to a secondary (alkylated) aromatic amine and quinoline to an amine, in which the amino-group has been changed into -N:CH-, and thus the feeble activity of the hydrogen atom in the *para*-position to the quinoline nitrogen atom may be accounted for.

Benzylidene aniline.

Quinoline.

For further study of the influence of the NH- and substituted NH-group on the reactivity of the *para*-hydrogen atom and on the basic character of the condensation products, diphenylamine, *N*-methyldiphenylamine, carbazole and *N*-methylcarbazole have also been condensed with different aldehydes. The feeble reactivity of the *para*-hydrogen atom in diphenylamine and the weak basic character of the compounds derived from it may be attributed to the phenylation of the amino-group but on methylation of the imino-hydrogen atom, the reactivity is increased to a remarkable extent although the basic character is slightly increased. Carbazole which was previously condensed with aldehydes in the presence of sulphuric

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acid or zinc chloride (Dutt, *Jr Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 502) condensed with benzaldehyde also in the presence of hydrochloric acid but less readily than diphenylamine, and the effect of methylation is not so marked as in diphenylamine; hence it appears that the influence of the NH-group is markedly affected when the nitrogen atom forms part of a ring.

A comparative study of the dyes derived from quinoline and tetrahydroquinoline shows that the tetrahydroquinoline complex exerts a stronger auxochromic influence than the quinoline complex and, therefore, although the dyes from tetrahydroquinoline are in a sense the reduction products of those from quinoline, yet they exhibit deeper shades as reduction causes the introduction of a stronger auxochrome (cf. indanthrene yellow which also gives a deeper colour (blue vat) on reduction).

A comparison of the influence of the auxochromic groups in the dyes derived from quinoline and tetrahydroquinoline is also interesting (*vide* Table IV). The condensation product of diphenylamine and benzaldehyde yields a disulphonic acid derivative, which, after oxidation, dyes silk and wool a green shade.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A. Dyes derived from Quinoline.

Phenyldiquinolylmethane.—A solution of pure synthetic quinoline (14 c.c.) dissolved in concentrated hydrochloric acid (37 per cent., 15 c.c.) and benzaldehyde (6 c.c.) is heated upon the water-bath for about 26 hours keeping the mouth of the flask open towards the end of the reaction. The product is extracted with 100 c.c. of water and made alkaline with caustic soda solution, when a light green product is obtained. The mixture is distilled in steam to free it from quinoline and benzaldehyde. The precipitate is washed with hot water, dissolved in dilute acetic acid and reprecipitated with ammonia, the process being repeated. The product is finally crystallised from a mixture of alcohol and acetic acid (1:1); yield, 30 per cent.

It is obtained as a light green powder readily soluble in acetic acid and nitrobenzene, fairly soluble in hot alcohol; insoluble in chloroform, carbon disulphide and benzene. The carbinol compound obtained by the oxidation of the leuco-base with freshly prepared lead peroxide, dyes wool, silk and tanned cotton a light green shade. (Found: N, 8.23. $C_{25}H_{19}N_2$ requires N, 8.09 per cent.).

Chloroplatinate.—0.2 G. of the leuco-base is dissolved in dilute hydrochloric and acetic acid (1:3) and 1 c. c. of platinum chloride (10%) is added when a precipitate is formed which is recrystallised from hot water in orange-yellow needles melting at 230° (decomp). (Found: Pt, 25.8. $(C_{25}H_{18}N_2)H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt, 25.8 per cent.).

Picrate.—0.4 G. of the leuco-base, in 2 c. c. of glacial acetic acid, is heated upon the water-bath with an alcoholic solution of picric acid for 1 hour. The mixture is poured into water and the precipitate thus obtained is recrystallised from water in golden yellow spangles melting at 199°. (Found: N, 12.4. $(C_{25}H_{18}N_2)C_6H_2(NO_2)_3OH$ requires N, 12.17 per cent.)

Other triphenylmethane dyes derived from quinoline are described below:

TABLE I.

Name and formula.	Method of preparation. (Q=quinoline).	M.p. and appearance.	P. c. of N : Calc. and found.	Properties.
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyldiquinolylmethane, $C_{26}H_{20}N_2O$	Q + anisaldehyde + conc. HCl on water-bath for 20 hrs.	Yellow micro-crystalline powder.	7.44; 7.46	Soluble in pyridine, acetic acid, mineral acids; insoluble in acetone, benzene and chloroform.
-Hydroxyphenyldiquinolylmethane, $C_{25}H_{18}N_2O$	Q + salicylaldehyde + conc. HCl on the water-bath for 26 hrs.	157-160°; yellow micro-crystalline powder.	7.73; 7.76	Soluble in caustic alkalis, sparingly so in cold mineral acids, insoluble in alcohol, acetone and benzene.
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyldiquinolylmethane, $C_{25}H_{18}N_2O$	Q + <i>p</i> -hydroxybenzaldehyde on water-bath + conc HCl for 26 hrs.	Does not melt below 263°; microcrystalline powder.	7.7; 7.0	Soluble in mineral and acetic acid, insoluble in benzene and chloroform.
<i>o</i> , <i>p</i> , <i>m</i> -Nitrophenyldiquinolylmethane, $C_{25}H_{17}N_2O_2$	Q + <i>o</i> , <i>p</i> , or <i>m</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde at 110-120° with conc. HCl for 17, 10, 26 hrs. respectively.	108° of <i>p</i> -compound; <i>ortho</i> and <i>meta</i> compounds could not be isolated in a very pure form.	10.74; 10.74 (<i>ortho</i>) 11.2 (<i>meta</i>) 10.88 (<i>para</i>)	All the three are soluble in mineral and acetic acids and insoluble in benzene and acetone.

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TABLE I—continued.

Name and formula.	Method of preparation. (Q = quinoline).	M.p. and appearance.	P.c. of N : Calc. and found.	Properties.
Dimethyl <i>p</i> -aminophenyldi-quinolylmethane, C ₂₇ H ₂₃ N ₃ .	Q + dimethyl- <i>p</i> -aminobenzaldehyde on water-bath with conc. HCl for 12 hrs.	168-170°; microcrystalline brown powder.	10.8; 11.9	Soluble in mineral and acetic acids and alcohol, insoluble in benzene and CS ₂ .
2 :4-Dioxyphenyldi-quinolylmethane, C ₂₅ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	Q + β-resorcylic aldehyde at 110° for 4 hrs. till the mixture assumes a deep violet colour with conc. HCl.	Does not melt below 240°; microcrystalline brown powder.	7.40; 7.87	Soluble in ammonia, caustic alkalis, alcohol and glacial acetic acid; insoluble in benzene and acetone.
(a) Monoacetyl derivative, C ₂₇ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	The carbinol compound + fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride.	Decomposes without melting; microcrystalline brown powder.	6.66; 6.60	Soluble in caustic alkalis; insoluble in most organic solvents; gives a deep red colour with FeCl ₃ .
(b) Diacetyl derivative, C ₂₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₄	Q + β-resorcylic aldehyde + acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate at 150-160°.	Does not melt below 287°; microcrystalline yellowish-brown powder.	6.06; 6.05	Soluble in glacial acetic acid; insoluble in alkalis, does not give coloration with FeCl ₃ .
(a) Disilver salt, C ₂₅ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ Ag ₂	Solution of the carbinol compound + alcoholic silver nitrate.	Red flakes.	Ag 36.5, 35.5	Crystallises from alcohol in red flakes.

B. Dyes derived from Tetrahydroquinoline.

m-Hydroxyphenyl-ditetrahydroquinolylmethane.—A mixture of tetrahydroquinoline (8 g.) *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (2.8 g.) and hydrochloric acid (25 c.c. of 20%) is heated on the water-bath for five hours. The mixture is made alkaline with dilute caustic soda solution, and is distilled in steam. The residue is dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and reprecipitated with ammonia and finally crystallised from alcohol. It is a microcrystalline, brown powder, soluble in mineral and acetic acids, in alcohol and acetone. It does not melt below 256°. The carbinol compound obtained by the oxidation of the leuco-base dyes wool and silk light brown shades. (Found: N, 7.42. C₂₅H₂₃N₂O requires N, 7.52 per cent.).

Other triphenylmethane dyes derived from tetrahydroquinoline are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Name and formula.	Method of preparation (T=tetrahydroquinoline)	M.p. and appearance.	P.c.of N : calc. and found.	Properties.
<i>m</i> -Nitro <i>p</i> -ditetrahydroquinolylmethane, $C_{25}H_{27}N_3O_2$	T + <i>m</i> -nitrobenzaldehyde on water-bath for 5 hrs. with 25% HCl.	212° (decomp.) ; lusturous green plates.	10'47; 10'8	Soluble in alcohol and acetone and insoluble in benzene.
Furfuryl-ditetrahydroquinolylmethane, $C_{23}H_{24}N_2O$	T + furfuraldehyde in alcohol on water-bath for 6 hrs. with 26% HCl.	Decomposes without melting; dark brown micro-crystalline powder.	8'14; 7'04	Sparingly soluble in acids and alkalis, insoluble in most organic solvents.
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-ditetrahydroquinolylmethane $C_{26}H_{28}N_2O$	T - anisaldehyde with 25 % HCl on water-bath for 6 hrs.	Microcrystalline green powder.	6'29; 7'38	Dissolves in conc. sulphuric acid (giving a green solution with red fluorescence), alcohol (giving a green solution) and in glacial acetic acid.
<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl ditetrahydroquinolylmethane, $C_{25}H_{26}N_2O$	T + salicylaldehyde on water-bath for 6 hrs. with 25% HCl.	163-164°; micro-crystalline yellow powder.	7'56; 7'90	Soluble in acids, insoluble in ether and acetone.
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl ditetrahydroquinolylmethane, $C_{25}H_{26}N_2O$	T + <i>p</i> -hydroxybenzaldehyde on the water-bath for 6 hrs. with 25% HCl.	255°; greenish plates.	7'56; 7'22	Soluble in mineral acid giving a green solution with a red fluorescence.
Dimethyl- <i>p</i> -aminophenyl-ditetrahydroquinolylmethane, $C_{27}H_{31}N_3$	T + dimethyl- <i>p</i> -aminobenzaldehyde with 25 % HCl.	Semi-solid at the ordinary temperature, solid at 10°.	10'58; 10'92	Soluble in mineral and acetic acids and alcohol insoluble in benzene.
2:4-Dioxyphenyl ditetrahydroquinolylmethane $C_{25}H_{26}N_2O_2$	T + <i>p</i> -resorcyaldehyde with 25% HCl.	Does not melt below 253°; microcrystalline red powder.	7'25; 7'32	Soluble in alcohol, insoluble in benzene.
Di- <i>N</i> -methyltetrahydroquinolylmethane, $C_{31}H_{36}N_2$	T + <i>N</i> -methyltetrahydroquinoline + formaldehyde with 30 % HCl.	Microcrystalline brown powder.	9'15; 9'81	Soluble in acids alcohol and acetone, insoluble in benzene and chloroform.
Phenyl-di- <i>N</i> -methyltetrahydroquinolylmethane, $C_{27}H_{30}N_2$	<i>N</i> -Methyltetrahydroquinoline + benzaldehyde with 25% HCl.	Sinters at 90°, melts at 100°; yellow micro-crystalline powder.	7'32; 7'30	Soluble in acetone and alcohol, insoluble in benzene and chloroform.

C. Dyes derived from Diphenylamine and Carbazole.

A mixture of diphenylamine (10 g.) dissolved in rectified spirit (30 c.c.), benzaldehyde (3 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid is heated upon the water-bath under reflux for 13 hours when a light green precipitate separates out. The product is washed repeatedly with boiling alcohol to remove any unaltered diphenylamine and benzaldehyde, dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid and poured into water when it is re-precipitated (yield, 50%). It is finally crystallised from a mixture of glacial acetic acid and absolute alcohol (2:1).

It is obtained as a green microcrystalline powder insoluble in most of the organic solvents except in nitrobenzene and hot glacial acetic acid and in concentrated sulphuric acid from which it is re-precipitated on dilution. When oxidised with lead peroxide in nitrobenzene solution and acetic acid a deep green product is obtained (Found: N, 6.76. $C_{31}H_{26}N_2$ requires N, 6.57 per cent.).

The Disulphonic Acid.—5 G. of the leuco-base are heated with 15 c.c. sulphuric acid (d 1.84) for 10 hours on the water-bath and poured into water when a brown precipitate is formed; it is washed with water and crystallised from alcohol in green plates soluble in water and alcohol. (Found: S, 10.6. $C_{31}H_{26}N_2S_2O_6$ requires S, 11.1 per cent.). When oxidised with lead peroxide it dyes wool and silk green shades.

TABLE III.

Dyes derived from Diphenylamine and Carbazole.

Name and formula.	Method of preparation.	M.p. and appearance.	P.c. of N: calc. and found.	Properties.
Dimethyldiphenyldiaminotriphenylmethane, $C_{33}H_{30}N_2$	<i>N</i> -methyldiphenylamine + benzaldehyde without any condensing agent upon water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr.	144-146°; greenish microcrystalline powder.	6.14; 6.32	Soluble in pyridine and glacial acetic acid (1:1) and nitrobenzene.
Phenyl-dicarbazole methane, $C_{31}H_{26}N_2$	Carbazole + benzaldehyde on water-bath with conc. HCl for 13 hrs.	Does not melt below 260°; faintly green powder.	6.63; 6.40	Soluble in pyridine, hot acetic acid, conc. sulphuric acid; insoluble in ether, benzene and chloroform.
Phenyldi- <i>N</i> -methylcarbazole methane, $C_{33}H_{36}N_2$	<i>N</i> -methylcarbazole + benzaldehyde with conc. HCl.	Bluish-green microcrystalline powder; sinters at 140°, melts at 148°.	6.22; 6.36	Soluble in glacial acetic acid and nitrobenzene.
Diphenyldiaminotriphenylmethane, $C_{25}H_{22}N_2$	Diphenylamine + formaldehyde + conc. HCl on the water-bath for 12 hrs.	Bluish-green powder.	8.0; 8.37	Insoluble in most organic solvents; soluble in nitrobenzene.

TABLE III—Continued.

Name and formula.	Method of preparation.	M.p. and appearance.	P.c. of N : calc. and found.	Properties.
Diphenyldimethyldiaminodiphenylmethane, $C_{27}H_{25}N_2$	N-methyldiphenylamine + formaldehyde without any condensing agent.	Dark green micro-crystalline powder.	7.40; 7.31	Soluble in nitrobenzene.
o-Hydroxyphenyldiphenyldiaminotriphenylmethane, $C_{31}H_{29}N_2O$	Diphenylamine + salicylaldehyde with conc. HCl.	Green powder.	6.33; 6.60	Soluble in alkalis, insoluble in most organic solvents.
3:4-Methylene-dioxyphenyldiphenyldiaminotriphenylmethane, $C_{32}H_{26}N_2O_2$	Diphenylamine + piperonal in alcoholic solution on water-bath for 12 hrs.	Light green micro-crystalline powder.	5.98; 6.16	Soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene and in conc. sulphuric acid.

TABLE IV.

Comparison of the Dyes derived from Quinoline and Tetrahydroquinoline.

Aldehyde employed.	Shades of dyes derived from quinoline.	Remarks.	Shades of dyes derived from tetrahydroquinoline.	Remarks.
Benzaldehyde.	Light bluish-green.	Auxochromic influence of quinoline feebly developed.	Bluish, green shade deeper than that from quinoline.	Influence of tetrahydroquinoline is evident.
Anisaldehyde.	Orange-yellow.	Green shade of the dye from quinoline is masked.	Light bluish-green.	Green shade is not masked.
Salicylaldehyde.	Light yellow.	Influence of OH is predominant.	Bluish-green.	Influence of OH not evident.
p-Hydroxybenzaldehyde.	Brownish-red.	OH in <i>para</i> position having greater influence than in <i>ortho</i> .	Bluish ash.	" "
m-Nitrobenzaldehyde.	Yellowish-green.	NO_2 has little auxochromic influence.	Bright green.	" "
o-, or p-Nitrobenzaldehyde.	Light green.	"	"	"
Dimethyl-p-aminobenzaldehyde.	Brown.	NMe_2 producing marked auxochromic effect.	Yellowish-brown.	NMe_2 in <i>para</i> position is sufficient to mask the green shade.
8-Besorcylaldehyde.	Orange.	Influence of two OH groups is noteworthy.	Reddish-brown.	Two OH groups change the green shade to reddish-brown.